

INTERNATIONAL MEDICAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL

ART OF MEDICINE

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ISBN: [978-0-578-26510-0](https://www.isbn-international.org/product/9780578265100)

The study of the functional reserve of the kidneys in the concomitant state of hypertension with diabetes mellitus.

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Abstract: Obesity-associated kidney disease with diabetes develops when several metabolic and hemodynamic factors interact, activating common intracellular signals, which, in turn, cause the production of cytokines and growth factors that form kidney failure. The mechanisms underlying glomerular hyperfiltration in the presence of obesity are widely discussed in the literature cardiovascular diseases, obesity, type II diabetes, and kidney dysfunction are becoming more and more pandemics of the 21st century. In recent years, the main cause of renal dysfunction is not its primary disease, but hypertension, it means essential arterial hypertension and diabetes mellitus.

Keywords: diabetes mellitus, arterial hypertension, podocyt, nephropathy, comorbidity, renal functional reserves.

Introduction. According to experts from the World Health Organization, the increase in the prevalence of chronic non-communicable diseases is considered an epidemic of the 21st century. Over the past decade, when it comes to comorbid conditions, the most frequently discussed continuum is cardiorenal disease. Cardiovascular disease, obesity, type II diabetes mellitus, kidney dysfunction, are increasingly common and become pandemics of the next century. The underlying cause of kidney dysfunction is not kidney disease, but rather a combined condition associated with hypertension (HT), namely essential arterial hypertension (AH) and diabetes mellitus.

According to the 2011 statistics on the prevalence of diabetes, 360 million patients were registered and the number is predicted to reach 552 million by 2030. It is known that irreversible severe changes in target organs occur in type II diabetes mellitus. Their number increases sharply with concomitant conditions, including GB. Concomitant diabetes mellitus and hypertension are detected in 60% of cases, which is a serious risk factor for cardiovascular diseases.

Obesity-associated kidney disease with diabetes develops when several metabolic and hemodynamic factors interact, activating common intracellular signals, which, in turn, cause the production of cytokines and growth factors that form kidney failure. The mechanisms underlying glomerular hyperfiltration in the presence of obesity are widely discussed in the literature [1]. The recognized mechanism is data on an increase in sodium reabsorption in the immediate vicinity of the tubules or the loop of Henle, leading to the development of tubuloglomerular feedback - an indirect decrease in the resistance of afferent arterioles, an increase in intracapsular pressure and glomerular filtration rate [27].

There are studies that show a decrease in glomerular hyperfiltration and damage to kidney tissue with weight loss [19]. The determination of markers of endothelial dysfunction is currently relevant in many diseases, including kidney diseases [17].

End-stage renal disease (ESRD) occurs when the estimated glomerular filtration rate (GFR) falls by at least 10% of normal. Among the main factors of progression of kidney damage in obesity are: insulin resistance (IR), hyperinsulinemia, dyslipidemia, impaired systemic and renal hemodynamics, ischemia of kidney tissues, auto- and paracrine effects of adipose tissue hormones [1, 21-22].

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a common chronic complex disease of rapidly growing global importance, accompanied by many complications, including retinopathy, neuropathy and nephropathy. Until 2017, the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) reported that around 452 million adults worldwide suffer from diabetes, and by 2045 this number could increase to 629 million[3,5]. Diabetic nephropathy (DN) is one of the most common microvascular complications of DM and a leading cause of ESRD, leading to high morbidity and mortality. The main pathological changes in DN are the accumulation of advanced glycation end products (AGEs), growth factors, and hemodynamic and hormonal variations that lead to proteinuria, hypertension, and a permanent decline in kidney function. However, previous research has shown that approximately 30-40% of patients with DM progress to ESRD [3,4,10], suggesting that genetic variations may influence the initiation and development of DN and ESRD. It is well known that gene susceptibility to DN plays an important role in humans, even under the same environmental exposure. Family clustering also confirms the importance of hereditary factors in DN and ESRD. Therefore, many genetic studies have been carried out to identify potential candidate genes in large diabetic cohorts [6,13], which may facilitate the study of the pathogenesis of DN. With the development of genetic methods, including studies of linkage and candidate genes, as well as studies of the study population, type of diabetes and phenotypes, it is not easy to understand the real effect of genetic variants. suggesting that genetic variation may influence the initiation and development of DN and ESRD. It is well known that gene susceptibility to DN plays an important role in humans, even under the same environmental exposure. Family clustering also confirms the importance of hereditary factors in DN and ESRD. Therefore, many genetic studies have been carried out to identify potential candidate genes in large diabetic cohorts [6], which may facilitate the study of the pathogenesis of DN. With the development of genetic methods, including studies of linkage and candidate genes, as well as studies of the study population, type of diabetes and phenotypes, it is not easy to understand the real effect of genetic variants. suggesting that genetic variation may influence the initiation and development of DN and ESRD. It is well known that gene susceptibility to DN plays an important role in humans, even under the same environmental exposure. Family clustering also confirms the importance of hereditary factors in DN and ESRD. Therefore, many genetic studies have been

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Hypertension is the second leading cause of ESRD after diabetes mellitus. According to statistics published by the US Renal Data System, hypertension accounts for 26% of post-diabetic ESRD patients, accounting for 38% [7,9,15]. Interestingly, the incidence of ESRD differs according to ethnic origin. Hypertension has been reported as a cause of ESRD in 35% of African Americans compared to only 25% of Caucasians in the US [2,11,18]. More recent studies have shown that African Americans are three times more likely to develop kidney disease than whites, especially those associated with hypertension, as they often develop CKD when systemic blood pressure rises to the range of mild to moderate hypertension at a young age [5,13, 27]. Another conclusion is that that hypertensive kidney disease is significantly more common among first- and second-degree relatives of patients with CKD than in individuals without a family history of CKD, suggesting that the predisposition of renal failure to hypertension is segregated in families [15,21,25]. These data indicate that progression to ESRD in hypertension is at least in part determined by hereditary factors. Kidney function can often be altered by altering renal hemodynamics, producing renal reactive oxygen species (ROS), promoting kidney fibrosis and inflammation, and decreasing podocyte function in hypertension, diabetes, obesity, and aging [4,17,19]. Regardless of underlying mechanisms , these studies provide an opportunity to manage the progression of CKD in patients with hypertension by changing the expression of causative genes, determining hereditary susceptibility. This review summarizes recent findings that highlight the identification of some of the genetic factors underlying predisposition to AHD in animal and human studies [9,16,24,26].

The occurrence of CKD in patients with cardiovascular diseases, including high blood pressure and diabetes, has been confirmed in a number of observations with an increase in mortality of 20-40 times compared with the general population.

For this reason, the assessment and early detection of the development of nephropathy, intravascular hypertension, and hyperfiltration in patients with essential arterial hypertension accompanied by diabetes mellitus is one of the important tasks of medicine.

Purpose: Determination of changes in the functional reserve of the kidneys and to study the correlation between its parameters with the excretion of Col4 depending on the duration of the disease in the concomitant state of hypertension with diabetes mellitus and in their separate observation.

Materials and methods: The object of the study was 135 patients aged 40-60 years, suffering from hypertension and concomitant type II diabetes mellitus, undergoing treatment at the Bukhara Regional Multidisciplinary Hospital. The patients were divided into 3 groups: group 1 consisted of 45 patients suffering from hypertension, group 2 consisted of 45 patients with hypertension and type II diabetes mellitus, group 3 included patients with type II diabetes.

In all patients, the level of cystatin C in the blood was determined, with its help, the GFR and the functional reserve of the kidneys, including the level of collagen IV in the urine, were determined. After taking blood for cystatin C, patients consumed in the morning egg white (lightly boiled or raw) without salt, mixed in the amount of 1 g per 1 kg of body weight in the range of 8:00-8.30 for 10-15 minutes. After it, after 1.5 hours, venous blood was taken again and the amount of cystatin C in each patient was determined. With the help of the determined indicator, the GFR was determined before and after the protein load, and on their basis the status of the functional reserve of the kidneys was assessed. To do this, the number obtained from afterload to afterload was divided by GFR after loading and multiplied by 100%. Depending on the results obtained,

Cystatin C concentration in urine was determined by immunoturbidimetry on an Abbott Architect c8000 analyzer using Cystatin C-AT reagent kits from Alfresa Pharma Corporation (Japan). Type IV collagen concentration was determined using Urinary Collagen IV EIA kits from DAIICHI FINE CHEMICAL CO.LTD (Japan).

Research results: The first group consisted of 45 patients (34 men and 11 women) with HD who were included in the study. Their mean age is 39.7 ± 3.1 years, systolic and diastolic blood pressure levels are 151 ± 7.8 and 92 ± 3.2 mm Hg. Art. respectively. The second group consisted of 45 patients (29 men and 16 women) with hypertension and type II diabetes mellitus, who had comorbidities and who had a diabetes compensation stage. Their mean age was 43.2 ± 4.6 years. The levels of systolic and diastolic blood pressure are 157 ± 8.2 and 95 ± 2.1 mm Hg, respectively. Art. Including, indicators of sugar, glycosylated hemoglobin in the blood amounted to 8.8 ± 1.2 mmol/l and 7.1 ± 0.85 mg%, respectively. All patients had a GFR level of 90 ml or more in 1 minute on a body surface of 1.73 m². The third group consisted of 45 people with type II diabetes mellitus (27 men and 18 women), while diabetes was in the compensation phase, blood sugar and glycosylated hemoglobin were 7.8 ± 1.1 mmol/l and 7.4 ± 1.2 mg%, respectively. Their mean systolic and diastolic blood pressures are 138 ± 4.8 and 91 ± 3.8 mmHg. Art. respectively. GFR for 1 minute was 90 ml and above on a body surface of 1.73 m².

Many studies have demonstrated the response of basal GFR to a variety of stimuli, from regular consumption of chicken and beef to amino acids and infusions of certain drugs in healthy individuals. In our study, we used egg white as the stimulus protein, and in the control group, we found an increase in GFR from 5.7% to 29.8% (average 13.8%). In the second group and the third group, a significantly lower glomerular response to protein load was found compared to the first group ($p < 0.001$), and this situation indicates that patients with diabetes mellitus and in combination with hypertension have a state of glomerular hypertension and hyperfiltration.

The average urinary excretion of type IV collagen in patients with DM did not differ from those in the first group. At the same time, 12 patients with DM had high excretion values ($>0.51 \mu\text{g}/\text{mmol}$ creatinine), which were not observed in the first group. This shows kidney damage is clearly higher in diabetic patients.

High excretion of type IV collagen was characteristic of patients with functional renal reserve according to CKD-EPI-cys in the range of 0--15% patients with a functional reserve of kidneys 0-5% ($p=0.003$).

Conclusions: With the duration of diseases that violate the functional structures of the kidneys, their functional reserve decreases. In comorbid conditions such as diabetes mellitus and hypertension, the reserve is used up and a low glomerular response to protein load can be obtained.

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